

The Influence of Work Abilities on Employee Performance at The Binjai City Tourism Office

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of work ability on employee performance at the Binjai City Tourism Office. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all company employees, with a total of 38 people. The research results show that work ability has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is shown by the T-count value of 3.756 which is greater than the T-table 1.685, and the P-Value value is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if work ability is increased by 1 unit, employee performance will increase by 0.931 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.221 or 22.10%, which indicates that work ability has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 77.90% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, work ability has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Binjai City Tourism Office. This identifies that, meaning, improvements in employee work abilities can contribute to improving employee performance.

Keywords: work ability; employee performance

INTRODUCTION

Employees have an important role in the life of an organization. Quality employees who perform well are very necessary because they can support the success of an organization itself. In order to achieve organizational success, it is necessary to manage and empower Human Resources (HR) that are creative, innovative, competitive and capable, (Kusuma et al., 2021). With human resource management (HR), there will be a periodic increase in the quality of human resources, namely an increase in effective work systems. Maximum performance from employees is something important and very necessary for the organization. One of the reasons why organizational goals are achieved more quickly is due to optimal employee performance, (Ananda et al., 2021).

Organizations must have Human Resources (HR) who are experts, qualified, proficient and experienced to achieve their goals in this increasingly advanced modern era. This organizational goal is important to achieve so that an organization can continue to develop and compete in the face of changes and developments over time. In order to achieve the goals that have been made, of course Human Resources (HR) has an important position in an organization, (Subagyo & Purnomo, 2022). Not only in companies, but also in government agencies, Human Resources (HR) also plays an important role in providing good services to the community.

Performance in general has the meaning of an individual's success in completing their work tasks. According to (Afandi, 2018), performance is the result that can be obtained by

an individual or group of people in a company based on their obligations and responsibilities to achieve goals that do not conflict with morality or law, (Afandi, 2018). Performance is something that is important to determine the progress of an organization or company, because the higher the employee's performance, the faster the organization will achieve its goals. (Kusjono & Ratnasari, 2019). Employee performance is one of the main factors in achieving success in an agency. Therefore, every agency must have employees with good performance so that they can realize the agency's overall goals.

One part of the government agency whose job is to handle the tourism sector is the Binjai City Tourism Office. In the tourism sector, the Binjai City Tourism Department is required to be able to seek and utilize existing potential, find solutions to problems and challenges, and serve and fulfill the needs of the community. Based on the results of field observations, in an effort to create superior employee performance, the Binjai City Tourism Department still seems to be facing obstacles that make it difficult to create maximum performance in achieving organizational goals. A situation that is still not suitable is found at the Binjai City Tourism Office, because there are still many problems such as employees who work but often arrive late, don't come to work without a reason, then rest early even though it's not yet break time, often leave the room even though it's still working hours. and the last is leaving work early, as a result this becomes a tradition and bad habit among employees. If this bad habit or culture is not handled and allowed to continue, it will definitely have a bad impact on the agency.

Work ability is one element of maturity which is related to knowledge and skills that can be obtained from education, training and experience. Work ability (ability) is the capacity of an individual to carry out various tasks in his work, (Robbins et al., 2017). Work ability is a variety of dynamic aspects, determination to develop, and also individual characteristics that have been systematically and negatively correlated with humanity, and systematically positively correlated with quality of work life, quality of life, productivity and general welfare. Indicators of work ability according to (Robbins et al., 2017) are as follows:

1) Work Ability

Employee work ability is a condition where an employee feels capable of completing the work given to him.

2) Education

Education is an activity to increase a person's knowledge, including increasing mastery of theory and decision skills regarding problems involving activities to achieve goals.

3) Years of service

Working period is the time required by an employee to work for a company.

4) Skills

A person's ability to operate work more quickly and easily.

5) Knowledge

Knowledge used to complete a job.

According to (Mangkunegara, 2016) The term performance comes from the words Job Performance or Actual Performance (work performance or actual achievements achieved by

someone. The definition of performance (work performance) is the quality and quantity of work results achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017) that is :

- 1) Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
- 2) Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.
- 3) Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.
- 4) Cooperate with other people at work.

The purpose of this research is to analyze and determine the effect of work ability on employee performance Binjai City Tourism Office. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous), (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). This research was carried out at the Binjai City Tourism Office. This research was carried out from March to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study is the entire number of employees at the Binjai City Tourism Office with a total of 38 employees with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

Status	Amount
Civil servants	23
Non civil servant	15
Total	38

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique when all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 38

employees. The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0. Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

- Y = Employee Performance
- X = Work ability
- a = Constant
- b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely work ability (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research results

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest scores, rating score and standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work ability	38	2.0	5.0	4,295	,8249
Performance	38	3.0	5.0	4,118	,5475
Valid N (listwise)	38				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the work ability and performance of employees at the Binjai City Tourism Office as above average, with mean values of 4.295 and 4.118 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.8249 for work ability and 0.5475 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of both variables. these variables.

Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for the Work Ability Variable (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KK1	0.667 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK2	0.844 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK3	0.880 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK4	0.821 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK5	0.867 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicator on the work ability variable has a correlation coefficient value of > 0.3202 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the indicator for the Work Ability variable is valid,(Sugiyono, 2018).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.715 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.690 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.793 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.656 > 0.3202	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.3202 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid.(Sugiyono, 2018).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) Reliability testing aims to measure how reliable or trustworthy the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at

the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Work ability	0.871	5
Employee Performance	0.676	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the work ability and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18,769	1,909	7,673	,000
	Work ability	,931	,870	,460	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 18.769 + 0.931X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 18.769 means that if there is no work ability, then there is an employee performance of 18.769 points. The work ability regression coefficient is 0.931, meaning that work ability influences an increase in employee performance by 0.931 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.425a	,180	,221	2,192

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Ability

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.221 or 22.10%, which means that work ability has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 77.90% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of work ability on employee performance at the Binjai City Tourism Office

Ha: There is an influence of work ability on employee performance at the Binjai City Tourism Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized		t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	18,769	1,909		7,673	,000
	Work ability	,931	,870	,460	3,756	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $3.756 > t$ table 1.685, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between work ability on employee performance at the City Tourism Office. Binjai.

Discussion

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Work Ability on Employee Performance, the findings of this research are in line with and strengthen the research results of Febriansyah, et al, (2020), and Syarifah Fadila, et al (2020), which stated that work ability has a significant positive influence on employee performance. The implication of the research results is that the variables Work Ability, Professionalism and Additional Income need to be maintained and improved. Therefore, employees of the Binjai City Tourism Office should improve their work abilities so that it will also have an impact on additional income which will also further improve employee performance. For example, getting additional income through promotions of tourist destinations in Binjai City. It is hoped that

these steps can further improve employee work abilities and professionalism, thereby improving employee performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of the hypothesis test show that transformational leadership has a positive effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the T-count value of $3.756 > T\text{-table } 1.685$ with a P-Value value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This regression coefficient shows that if Work Ability is increased by 1 unit, then the change in employee performance as seen from the Y value will increase by 0.931 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially, Work Ability has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Binjai City Tourism Office.
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.221 or 22.10%, which means that Work Ability has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 77.90% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the discussion and conclusions above, the following suggestions can be implemented by the Binjai City Tourism Office to improve employee performance and:

1. Institutions are advised to hold regular training and workshops to improve employee work abilities. Training programs that are relevant to employees' duties and responsibilities can help them develop the skills and knowledge needed to improve performance
2. The application of transformational leadership must continue to be encouraged to improve employee performance. Leaders who are able to inspire and motivate employees, as well as encourage innovation and continuous improvement, will have a positive impact on overall institutional performance.

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